

This document forms section seven of the University of Bath's Responsible Research Assessment Guidance and should be read alongside [the full guidance](#). You can find more information on the [RRA webpage](#).

7. Practical examples of ways to assess research outputs responsibly

Key points from this section:

- Choose an assessment approach that matches the context and purpose.
- Read our practical examples about options for assessment to ensure fair and responsible evaluation

There are different ways to assess a research output or portfolio of outputs. Below are some practical examples.

These options are not exhaustive. Departments, teams, and individuals should consider the appropriateness of these options for their local context and develop alternatives where required.

Option A: Assess the research output (or multiple outputs if assessing a portfolio)

Individual's submission: The individual supplies a link to or attachment of their research outputs. When assessing a portfolio, the individual selects their top three to five research outputs to put forward. It is not expected or realistic for assessors to read all of an individual's outputs – particularly if the individual is later in their career.

Entity submission: The entity selects an appropriate number of outputs (for example, five to ten), depending on its size and the scale of assessment.

Review: Outputs are reviewed by a diverse panel with expertise appropriate to the subject area. Reviewers understand responsible research assessment (RRA) and avoid metrics listed in Table 2. They recognise that assessing the content of an output based on novelty, significance, rigour, and design is much more important than the publication venue.

Most suitable if:

- reviewers are in a similar field and will be capable understanding the quality (novelty, significance, and rigour) by reviewing the output themselves; and
- reviewers have time to thoroughly read the output.
- the aim is to understand the individual's capability through their selected outputs.

Less suitable if:

- reviewers are not expert in the field; or
- reviewers are time-poor; or
- there is a high volume of outputs or individuals to assess.
- you would like to formally consider reach, visibility, impact.
- for the assessment of entities - unless the entity is the only affiliation (e.g. some Institutes/ groups) it may be unclear how the entity contributed to or aligns with the output.

Notes: If the output(s) are multi-author, and CRediT taxonomy is not used, it might be difficult to assess the individual's contribution.

Option B: Assess an individual's/entity's statement of their research output(s)

Individual's submission: The individual provides a statement (approximately 200 words) to describe

- 1) their contribution to the output;
- 2) its quality (novelty, significance, rigour).
- 3) its reach, visibility and impact (if required by the assessor).

The statement should not use any of the metrics listed as 'Avoid' in Table 2. Individuals should reference the best possible evidence options from Tables 3-5. Where an individual's research portfolio is being assessed, the individual should develop a statement for each of their top three to five research outputs.

Entity submission: As above, but reviewers may consider asking for a single statement which captures the entities' contribution to the outputs, their quality, and reach, visibility, and impact for five to ten outputs.

Review: A diverse panel of reviewers, familiar with the subject area, should offer primary assessment of the *claims* of novelty, significance and rigour in the field. Reviewers understand RRA principles, avoid any of the metrics listed as 'Avoid' in Table

2 and recognise that assessing the individual's description of content is far more important than the publication venue.

Most suitable if:

- reviewers are in adjacent fields and capable of assessing the claims to quality. Where reach and/or visibility is also assessed, the reviewer sufficiently understands the disciplinary norms to judge significance.
- reviewers do not have the time or expertise to interpret the quality, significance or rigour based on a review of the output themselves.
- the process includes recruitment processes with a question about outputs on the application form.

Less suitable if:

- reviewers are distant from the subject matter.

Option C: Assess an individual's or entities description of their contribution to the generation of new ideas, tools, methodologies or knowledge

Individual's submission: The individual completes the section of a narrative CV (e.g., [R4RI by UKRI](#)) that relates to their ability to generate new ideas, tools, methodologies, or knowledge. The individual is instructed to avoid metrics listed in Table 2 and refer to best possible evidence options in Tables 3- 5.

Entities submission: As per 'individual submission', but complete with a focus on evidence of their collective ability to generate new ideas, tools, methodologies, or knowledge.

Reviewer: A diverse panel close to the subject area reviews and understands the assessment of quality provided.

Most suitable if:

- reviewers would prefer to assess a single statement that captures multiple outputs and contributions.
- the goal is to understand the candidate's broader research capabilities and assess outputs quality in the context of other contributions to quality research (e.g. impact, research projects etc)
- reviewers are in adjacent fields and capable of assessing the claims to quality.
- recruitment processes will include a question about research contributions on the application form.

Less suitable if:

- the process concerns international recruitment. There is some early evidence¹ to suggest that international markets are less familiar with the narrative CV format, and roles attract fewer international applications when a narrative CV is required.

These examples are not exhaustive and are not the only options for assessing research outputs. Teams and departments retain flexibility to design assessment processes that are appropriate to their context, provided they are in line with the University's principles of research assessment and the guidance outlined in this document.

For more information read [the full guidance](#) or visit the [RRA webpage](#).

¹ Adams E., Casci T., Padgett M, Lab for Academic Culture, University of Glasgow, Alfred J., Catalyst Editorial, 2021. *Narrative CVs* [Online]. University of Glasgow. Available from: https://www.gla.ac.uk/media/Media_1059370_smx.pdf [Accessed 19 November 2025]